

How can Large Language Models Assist in Journal Classification? A Study of Performance and Limitations

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Abstract

This research explores the capabilities of Large Language Models (LLMs) as assistants in classifying journals and conference proceedings into disciplines. This is particularly relevant for smaller journals in fields like Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH), which are often absent from major databases and therefore lack standardized classification. We evaluate their effectiveness using three datasets: (1) an extended sample from the Flemish bibliographic database for SSH (VABB-SHW), combining manual and international databases classifications; (2) a smaller, manually classified subset from the same database; and (3) the Norwegian journal list, which assigns a single discipline per publication, unlike the multi-label structure of the Flemish dataset.

We analyze both open and closed models of different sizes, including multilingual BERT, GPT-4o, GPT-4o-mini, Gemini-1.5 Pro, Gemini-1.5 Flash, Mistral-7B-Instruct, and DeepSeek-V3. We also experiment with various prompting strategies to assess their impact on classification performance.

Results show that smaller models benefit from a reduced number of candidate labels, though this can introduce errors. Providing models with custom examples that share high embedding similarity with the target instance improves classification in most cases. Journals indexed in multiple databases are classified more accurately than those with limited representation. Single-label and multi-label classification each present distinct advantages depending on the context.

While LLMs exhibit agreement levels comparable to human annotators, they require human supervision. Without internet access and explicit refusal mechanisms, models tend to guess classifications based on journal names, leading to misclassification. These findings highlight both the potential and limitations of integrating LLMs into journal classification.

Introduction

Accurate classification of academic journals plays a crucial role in research evaluation, bibliometrics, and funding decisions. Various methods are currently employed, several of which rely on journal-to-journal citation networks (Archambault et al., 2011; Wang & Waltman, 2016). However, these approaches face limitations, especially when confronted with situations where citation information is lacking or incomplete, such as in the Social Sciences and Humanities. With the advancement of Generative Large Language Models (LLMs), this research aims to explore whether, at their current level, these models can assist in classifying journals using limited information, such as the journal name and ISSN(s). We also test different prompting strategies to see if we can improve accuracy by limiting the model's choices, offering custom examples, and using prompt chaining. Having an automatic classification system paired with a human evaluator could increase the speed and the quality of the classification and decrease the amount of manual work required. This could be particularly useful for two use-cases: one at a local level and one at an international level.

First, at the local level, having research output classified into disciplines offers a tool for discipline-aware research and reporting, which considers the various discipline-specific research traditions and ensures a fair evaluation across disciplines. This is particularly important when funding is involved – as is the case of performance-based research funding systems (Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (European Commission) et al., 2018; Zacharewicz et al., 2019). Although journal classification exists in large international databases like Web of Science (WoS) and Scopus, many studies show that these databases inadequately cover Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) publications and publication channels, especially non-English ones (Archambault et al., 2006; Chavarro et al., 2018; Mongeon & Paul-Hus, 2016; Petr et al., 2021; Pölönen et al., 2021). As a result, national databases have been built for the purpose of comprehensive research evaluation. These often include additional publication channels that are not present and classified in any of the international databases. Such is the case for VABB-SHW database in Flanders, Belgium, which has been developed to comprehensively cover peer-reviewed publications written by SSH researchers from the five Flemish universities. VABB-SHW reports were originally solely based on classification based on authors' departments, but it has been enriched with channel-based cognitive classification of the publications (Guns et al., 2018). Journals (identified by ISSN) and books (identified by ISBN) are classified into one or more OECD FORD disciplines. The process primarily relies on classifications in external sources, like Web of Science, Scopus, and ISSN.org. However, remaining ISSNs and ISBNs (not classified elsewhere or classification cannot be mapped to OECD FORD) are classified manually. To reduce the reviewer bias and increase the classification accuracy, these journals and books are classified by two reviewers, and the results are then combined. One of the purposes of this study is to evaluate if a generative LLM could serve as one of the reviewers, thus reducing the amount of manual work.

Secondly, at an international level, various databases have distinct strategies for research classification, resulting in incongruences when they are integrated with each other (Archambault et al., 2011). Although various methodologies exist to align distinct classifications, they often require either many assumptions and approximations or manual classification that, as shown in the results section, is often biased. If the classification done by LLM aligns with the expected classification or at least is justified in most cases, it might offer a good alternative as a first classification that can then be further refined. Over the past two decades, there has been an increasing focus on paper-level classification, which aims to provide a more precise representation of a publication's content than journal-level classification. Numerous studies (Glänzel et al., 1999; Shu et al., 2019; Waltman & van Eck, 2012; Zhang & Shen, 2024) have investigated its advantages in offering a more content-specific classification. As a result, journal classification is often compared to publication-level classification in terms of its ability to accurately represent research content.

However, journal-level classification remains important, as the variety of research practices across disciplines is more apparent and representative at the level of journals than at the level of individual publications. Journals are usually supported, maintained, and built around a research community, or, in the case of some big journals, several research communities. For this reason, when using field normalization of the scientific indicators (Waltman & van Eck, 2019), it makes more sense to do it at the level of a journal if the goal of the normalization is to reflect the variety of and the distinctions among research cultures. This distinction is evident in how different journals frame similar topics. For example, a study on machine learning applications in scientific publications may emphasize technical advancements and computational methods in the ACL Anthology, while a similar study in Scientometrics might focus on bibliometric implications and scientific output analysis. Therefore, although the journal-level classification and paper-level classification may overlap (Shu et al., 2019), they provide distinct information regarding the article.

One of the consistent issues emphasized in the literature regarding journal-level classification is the presence of multidisciplinary journals (Glänzel et al., 1999; Waltman & van Eck, 2012, 2019; Zhang & Shen, 2024). Their existence makes it difficult to fully investigate the research covered by a set of publications using only journal classification, as they often cover publications from a large number of disciplines and subdisciplines (Zhang & Shen, 2024). However, arguably, when accounting for publishing practices, these journals have their own tradition in how research is presented and an important role of connecting various research communities and keeping them up to date with the progress in research across disciplines, therefore giving perspective.

Journal classification can be based either on inherent journal attributes – such as title, ISSN and examples of publication titles – or on the citation network positioning. Here we focus on the former, as citation-based classification presents specific challenges for SSH due to its insufficient coverage in major international citation databases. Although the need for a more

comprehensive overview of science, particularly in SSH, has led to the creation of local databases, these usually lack citation information. Furthermore, citations in SSH often have a slower post-publication rate, delaying the point at which citation-based classification can provide an accurate representation of a publication's place in the literature (Archambault & Larivière, 2010).

In the next section, we present the literature review on journal classification systems, including how classification is achieved, followed by a literature review on the use of LLMs in classification tasks, highlighting their advantages and limitations. Then, we introduce the datasets used for evaluation, including their specificities. Next, we introduce our methodology, covering the classification process, variations of the prompting strategies and the evaluation. We then analyze the results for each dataset, including the agreement between models and human annotators. Finally, we conclude by discussing our findings, research limitations, and potential directions for future work.

The results follow the chronological progression of our research questions. First, we examine ways to reduce the amount of irrelevant information provided to the LLM by identifying criteria to narrow down the number of disciplines presented as classification options. Secondly, we analyze the results for manually classified journals and conference proceedings from the latest VABB-SHW and compare it with human classification, assessing the potential of LLMs as second annotator. Third, we examine whether expanding the dataset to a larger sample of VABB-SHW journals and conference proceedings, which have broader representation in international databases, leads to improved results. Finally, we compare the model's performance in single-label versus multi-label classification using the Norwegian journal list to determine whether classification accuracy is influenced by the number of assigned disciplines.

Literature Review

Approaches to Journal Classification: Methodologies and Implementations

The classification of journals is a well-established task that has been approached differently across various systems and countries. As previously mentioned, two prominent examples are WoS and Scopus, both of which use journal classification as their primary classification method. However, they employ different strategies: WoS classifies journals into one or multiple science categories based on expert evaluation and citation analysis (Leydesdorff & Rafols, 2009), while Scopus relies on the assessment of the journal's title and content by in-house experts¹.

In addition to international databases and their classification methodologies, numerous other systems and approaches have been proposed for journal classification. Among these, Archambault et al. (2011) introduce a three-level hierarchical taxonomy, building on existing

¹ https://service.elsevier.com/app/answers/detail/a_id/12007/c/10546/supporthub/scopus/

classifications to better incorporate both modern research fields and multidisciplinary journals. The authors advocate for a single-label classification approach, which also aligns with the single-label classification approach used in the Norwegian journal list. Glänzel & Schubert (2003) proposed a classification scheme specifically for scientometrics analysis, recommending a two-step process: first, classifying journals with a clear disciplinary focus and then applying paper-level classification for multidisciplinary journals. Börner et al. (2012) developed a classification system consisting of 13 disciplines and 554 subdisciplines, derived through clustering, as part of their effort to build a map of science using WoS and Scopus data. Chinese Library Classification (CLC) serves as China's national library classification scheme, assigning a Chinese Serial Number (CSN) to every academic journal published in the country. The CSN consists of a registration number and the classification code, which is assigned upon journal registration (Shu et al., 2019).

Generative models for classification and labeling tasks

Generative LLMs were initially designed to be unsupervised multitask learners capable of using the knowledge from a large and diverse dataset to perform multiple tasks (Radford et al., 2019). This characteristic is particularly useful in cases where a large, labeled dataset of good quality is not available – a common challenge for local journal data. However, Sun et al., 2023 identify two reasons for which LLMs underperform compared to fine-tuned models for text classification: the task requires strong reasoning abilities to resolve complex linguistic phenomena and the LLMs are constrained by maximum context length limitations. Over the last two years, the latter constraint has significantly lessened with context length increasing to up to 2 million tokens with Gemini 1.5 Pro and 128 000 tokens for GPT-4o (2024-08-06 version), making the issue of context length obsolete for most problems. Our study explores whether LLMs can effectively leverage their pre-trained knowledge to compensate for the limited journal information available in the classification task. Unlike traditional approaches that rely on explicit feature extraction and labeled data, LLMs have the potential to integrate patterns and domain-specific information learned during pretraining.

Another important dimension of LLM-based classification is the choice between open, closed, large, or small language models, as explored by Yu et al. (2023). The advantage of open-source models is the full control that they provide to users. Moreover, as these models can be deployed anywhere, they address privacy concerns (although closed models often offer opt-out settings to prevent data sharing). However, until recently, open-source models often lagged behind closed models in terms of performance and services associated to them. The recent launch of the DeepSeek models (DeepSeek-AI, Guo, et al., 2025) has the potential of evening the balance. Nevertheless, deploying open-source models comparable in performance with the closed ones requires a lot of computational power and it is not always feasible for small projects. Meanwhile, using an API service presents similar concerns and challenges as closed ones.

Additionally, multiple studies (Bucher & Martini, 2024; Li et al., 2024; Mayer et al., 2023; Yu et al., 2023) have shown that a fine-tuned smaller models can outperform the non-fine-tuned larger language models on a specific task. Fine-tuning LLMs could further enhance performance, but this comes with an increased cost – either from the cost of training and further interrogating the closed models or from the computational resources that are used for the open ones. However, when generalizability is required or when there is a lack of enough train instances, LLMs remain preferable (Y. Chae & Davidson, 2023; Yu et al., 2023) due to their larger size and greater amount of stored information.

Data

This research evaluates our methodology on three different datasets with distinct characteristics in terms of the difficulty of the journals in the test data, the languages of the journals, and the number of labels per journal. Two datasets are derived from VABB-SHW, both using multilabel classification, while the Norwegian journal list uses a single label classification.

For the datasets based on VABB-SHW, the training data for classification using mBERT (see Methodology section for details) is enriched with 9,455 journals and conference proceedings from the Science Citation Index Expanded (Web of Science) to improve representation of non-SSH disciplines. Overlap with the test data was verified and explicitly excluded. This enrichment is necessary because the database primarily consists of SSH channels, leading to insufficient representation of non-SSH disciplines in the training data. Additionally, non-SSH journals and conference proceedings may appear in the test data, as some are authored by Flemish SSH researchers.

VABB-SHW extended journal list

VABB-SHW is the Flemish database for publications authored by researchers from SSH departments from universities in Flanders, Belgium. The database is updated annually with new publications submitted by the universities. The original classification in the database is organizational, based on the authors' affiliation. However, it has since been enriched with the classification of publication channels (journals, conference proceedings, and books).

The process of classifying journals and conference proceedings into disciplines is fully explained by Guns et al. (2018). Most newly added journals and conference proceedings are classified using external databases. However, some publication channels cannot be retrieved this way, resulting in some part of the journals and conference proceedings being manually classified.

In total, this dataset currently contains 27,447 unique, valid ISSNs identified as journals and conference proceedings. Of these, 12,617 ISSNs are associated with multiple journal or conference titles, either due to title variations, special editions, or, in the case of conferences, different iterations of the same event. To address this, additional preprocessing steps were applied to consolidate these records into a single title per ISSN.

Given the multilabel nature of the data, a completely balanced dataset is difficult to achieve. However, we have tried to extract test data that give us enough information to analyze various aspects of the classification. More precisely,

- mix between single label and multilabel journals for each discipline
- mix between publications in English and publications in Dutch for each discipline to evaluate the models' capabilities on both languages
- three levels of complexity as described below.

Three levels of complexity are assigned using the presence of the journal in various databases. Currently, we have journal information from 6 sources: WoS, Scopus, ISSN.org, OCLC, DOAJ and manual classification. Manual classification is performed only when the journal was not found in any of the other data sources. If the previously manually classified journals are found in one or more international databases in the subsequent years, their classification gets updated for coherence reasons. We base the journal's classification complexity on its potential visibility to the model through the train data. We assume the journals that are widely present in the international databases and better indexed to have a higher chance of being previously seen by the current LLMs. The three levels of complexity are defined as following:

- *low* if the journals have been found in 4-5 sources outside "manual"
- *medium* if the journals can be found in 2-3 sources outside "manual"
- *high* if the journals have not been found in any external source or was found in only one external source

VABB-SHW manual data

Each year, journals and conference proceedings that require manual classification are reviewed individually. This dataset consists of publication channels with an ISSN, that were manually classified in the 2024 iteration.

Each channel is classified by two reviewers from the research group and their results are combined. If both classifications fully agree, this serves as the final classification. If there is any discrepancy, the final classification is determined by the person combining the classifications. We use the final classification as ground truth for this analysis.

In practice, we use as training data all the classified journals and conference proceedings in the database from the previous years and the ones retrieved from external databases this year – 27 198 journals and conference proceedings in total – further supplemented by the WoS data. The test data consist of 249 channels² that were manually classified this year. We expect overall poor results for this dataset given its increased difficulty (*high* according to the previously defined scale). Most journals in this set are not well-known and are challenging to

² These channels include mostly journals and conference proceedings, however they also contain books from various book series that have an ISSN.

classify, even for human annotators, due to the lack of easily accessible information. This lack of information may also contribute to a higher likelihood of LLM hallucination during classification.

Norwegian data

For completeness, we have included an additional dataset in our analysis, distinct from VABB-SHW. Specifically, we apply our methodology to journal and conference proceedings data from the Norwegian repository³.

Compared to VABB-SHW, the dataset assigns only one discipline per journal, simplifying the classification task from a multi-label to a single-label problem. Additionally, unlike VABB-SHW, which predominantly covers Social Sciences and Humanities, the Norwegian comprises all the disciplinary areas.

In total the repository has 38 899 journals classified into one of the 73 NPI Scientific Fields of the Norwegian Publication Indicator. Records not assigned to any of the 73 NPI Scientific Fields (2 798 records) are removed from our analysis.

We have automatically mapped the journals classified under 68 NPI Scientific Fields to our extended version of OECD FORD classification. The remaining five – “Romance Studies”, “Germanic Studies”, “Scandinavian Studies”, “Classical Studies”, “Slavonic Studies” – have been manually assigned to an OECD FORD discipline. A total of 823 records were manually classified as either “Literature” or “Languages and Linguistics”, while three records were classified to a different category. The column “Original Title” is retained as the title to be used for classification.

The dataset provides the language of each journal, but since we are primarily interested in the language of the journal title, and 2,737 journals are labeled as "Multiple languages", we used the langdetect library to determine the title's language. A total of 25,554 journals were classified as English and 10,546 as non-English.

Our test set is structured to include a maximum of 15 examples per discipline for English journals and at least 15 for non-English journals, resulting in 30 examples per discipline. After mapping, 32 FORD disciplines remain represented, resulting into a total of 960 test instances.

The remaining 35,141 instances form our training set.

Methodology

One of the core methodological questions for this research consists in designing relevant prompts for journal classification that result in a good quality classification when given to generative LLMs. Figure 1 shows the high-level scheme of the experiment. The prompt contains clear explicit instructions and three contextual components:

³ <https://kanalregister.hkdir.no/publiseringskanaler/AlltidFerskListe>

1. Discipline information, which both defines the classification scope by listing disciplines and providing descriptions to distinguish among them.
2. Journal information used to identify and evaluate the journal
3. Examples, which are presented as simulated exchanges between a human and the assistant LLM. These reinforce the instructions regarding the number of disciplines and the required output format.

Figure 1: High-level scheme of the experiment.

****INSTRUCTIONS****

Hi, you are a librarian trying to categorize journals according to their disciplines.

Here is a Python dict with disciplines as keys and descriptions as value:

{discipline_description_dict}

The input you get is a dictionary with the title and the ISSN of the journal.

****OUTPUT FORMAT****

Output should be a Python list containing the disciplines in which the journal has been classified. Only return the list of disciplines. No other text, explanations, or details. Only disciplines from the provided dictionary. Predict at least one discipline. You can select up to {n} disciplines. If the journal is too diverse, classify it as "multidisciplinary".

****RULES****

- Return only the Python list of disciplines.
- The list should only contain disciplines from the provided dictionary.

Prompt 1: System prompt for classification

Prompt 1 shows the system prompt used for classification when the model supports it. A system prompt is a predefined instruction that guides the model's behavior and takes priority over other prompts. Here, it is followed by the examples modeled as User-Assistant exchanges, where the Assistant's response emulate the model's expected answers, reinforcing the rules and output format.

However, variations are possible for each element of this scheme. Through our research, we have experimented with several combinations of variations of the input data, prompting strategy and the generative models with the goal of achieving an accurate journal classification.

Journal information

Each dataset contains similar information about the journals: their name, ISSN(s), and examples of articles. Throughout our experiments, we have used both the journal name and ISSN(s) to help identify the correct journal for classification. The ISSN is particularly useful because journal names can sometimes be ambiguous, change over time, or have variations across publishers and regions. As a unique and stable identifier, the ISSN helps reduce inconsistencies in classification. Additionally, since LLMs may have been trained on sources that include journal-related information, providing the ISSN may assist in retrieving the correct reference when the model recognizes it, contributing to more reliable classification. We have also conducted experiments leveraging the example of publications as additional information about the content of a journal to test if it results in an improvement of the metrics.

Additionally, a further exploration of the information that LLMs have about these journals has been conducted with the hypothesis that it would help clarify the basis for the classification and give more context to the classification prompt.

Figure 2: Process for retrieving the model's knowledge of a channel, if recognized

Figure 2 represents an extension of the Journal Information cell that contains only the journal name and ISSN. More precisely, the model is asked if it has information regarding the Aims and Scope of the journal, Abstracts, Keywords, Published Articles, Editorial Board, Submission

Guidelines, Special Issues, or Indexing Information, with the assumption that any of these would offer further insight into the topic of the journal. After getting the list of characteristics that the model claims to have access to, we are prompting it to write a one paragraph summary for each of the available characteristics individually. This information is then further summarized in two paragraphs that are used together with the Journal Name and ISSN as input information about the journal for the purpose of its classification. We test the accuracy of this approach on a limited number of journals to evaluate its informative value.

Number of disciplines and discipline information

In this study we are using the OECD FORD classification for the journal classification. More specifically, we use a slightly adapted version of OECD FORD, which is more granular at the level of humanities (Figure 3): “History and archaeology” is split into “History” and “Archaeology”, “Languages and literature” into “Languages and linguistics” and “Literature”, and “Philosophy, ethics and religion” into “Philosophy and ethics” and “Religion”. Each discipline is characterized by a description as provided by OECD FORD with modifications for the Humanities disciplines that have been extended. This classification is the one that is currently used in Flanders, more specifically in the VABB database for both organizational and journal classification as it is integrated into several research evaluations tasks, so coherence and the existence of a well-established system is required (Pölonen et al., 2021).

For each discipline, we have generated 100 keywords with GPT-4o starting from the name of the discipline and the description and then manually curated the list to retain only significant keywords.

Figure 3: OECD FORD classification scheme with extended differentiation for Humanities.

In our previous experiments using the same list of disciplines for abstract classification (Arhiliuc et al., 2024) with GPT-3.5-turbo, we concluded that the large number of disciplines and definitions have a negative influence on the classification. While the newer models can handle more information of increased complexity, we aim to test if reducing the number of disciplines the model has to choose from results in an increase of the quality of the classification.

For this purpose, we are using embedding proximity, measured by cosine similarity, between a vector representation of the journal and another one directly or indirectly representative of the discipline. Several embedding models were tested to determine which one would best support this task. These embeddings serve to calculate a reduced list of disciplines to then be proposed to the generative LLM as options for classification. We refer to that list as the *selected disciplines list*.

Vector representation of the journal:

- Embedding of the journal name
- Embedding of the journal name + up to three examples of article titles

Vector directly representative of the discipline:

- Embedding of discipline name + discipline description
- Embedding of discipline name + list of keywords
- Average embedding of discipline keywords

Vector indirectly representative of the discipline:

- Embedding of train journal names
- Embedding of train journal names + up to three examples of titles
- Embedding of individual keywords

For the vectors directly representative of the disciplines, the selected disciplines list is created by taking the top n disciplines with the embeddings closest to the journal vector. In this case, the final number of disciplines in the list (n) can be predefined.

For the vectors indirectly representative of the disciplines, we select the top m journals or keywords that are the closest in embeddings to the journal embedding. Then, we extract and deduplicate the disciplines associated with these keywords and journals. In this case, we cannot predetermine the number of disciplines.

The goal of the selected disciplines list is to reduce the number of disciplines proposed to the generative LLM as options while maintaining the true disciplines in the list, otherwise we are introducing additional errors in the classification process. Thus, the list is evaluated according to three criteria (Table 1).

Table 1: Criteria for evaluating strategies to reduce the number of labels

Criterion	Notation	Goal
Average number of disciplines	N	Decrease the value
Proportion of journals with all true disciplines in the selected disciplines list	$Prop_{journals}$	Increase the value towards 1

Average proportion of true disciplines in the selected disciplines list across journals	$Prop_{true_labels}$	Increase the value towards 1
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For example, for Journal 1 with true labels [L1, L2, L8, L9] and list of 5 suggested labels [L1,L3,L5,L6,L7] - $\frac{1}{4}$ true labels are represented. For Journal 2 with true labels [L2, L5] and list of 4 suggested labels [L1, L2, L4, L5], the proportion of true labels represented is 1 (100%). In the case of this 2-journals dataset, $N = \frac{5+4}{2} = 4.5$, $Prop_{journals} = \frac{1}{2} = 0.5$, $Prop_{true_labels} = \frac{0.25+1}{2} = 0.625$. From now on, the evaluation of this task will be represented by triplets $(N, Prop_{journals}, Prop_{true_labels})$. This particular example is represented by (4.5, 0.5, 0.625)

Examples

The examples fed to the LLM fall into two categories: random and custom.

- Random examples are selected from the training data based solely on ensuring coverage of all possible label counts (e.g., 1 to 3 labels in the case of VABB-SHW).
- Custom examples are chosen based on cosine similarity between embeddings, selecting journals most similar to the one being classified, while still maintaining diversity in label count. For VABB-SHW, this means selecting the closest journal among those with one label, the closest journal among those with two labels, and the closest journal among those with three labels. Meanwhile, for the Norwegian dataset, this involves selecting the three closest journals or conference proceedings, ensuring they have a relative Levenshtein distance below 0.85 from the original journal to avoid near-duplicates.

The goal of comparing random and custom examples is to determine whether providing examples more similar to the journal being classified impacts the model's classification behavior and consistency.

Evaluation

The evaluation for all the datasets is done by calculating the micro F_1 -score of the classification.

The F_1 metric combines both precision and recall, thereby considering both how many predicted disciplines are true and how many of the true disciplines are predicted.

$$F_1 = 2 \frac{precision \cdot recall}{precision + recall}$$

For the case of VABB-SHW, where we have access to the manual classification of two reviewers, we compare the agreement rate between reviewers and between each reviewer

and the LLMs and manually analyze the differences to identify where the models are making the most errors and whether the errors make sense given the context.

Models

BERT multilingual (mBERT)

As a baseline, we use multilingual BERT⁴ trained on:

- the training data + additional WoS journal classification data to balance the dataset for non-SSH journals for VABB-SHW dataset
- the training data for the Norwegian dataset

Multilingual BERT is a multilingual variation of a transformer-based family of models following a Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) architecture (Devlin et al., 2019). It has been trained on Wikipedia data for 104 languages⁵, including English, Dutch, Norwegian, German, and French which are prevalent in our datasets. This is a relevant baseline, as there are several research papers (Y. (YJ) Chae & Davidson, 2023; Yu et al., 2023) that show that smaller models fine-tuned on the data and for the task have outperformed previous iterations of large language models.

GPT-4o and GPT-4o-mini

GPT-4o, a new flagship model from OpenAI has been launched in May 2024 as a larger and more performant multimodal generative model. It has been shown in benchmarks to outperform previous iterations of the GPT models and most competitors at the launch time (Liu et al., 2024; OpenAI, 2024a). One month later, a smaller version of the model has been released with less parameters and reduced cost, yet also shown to outperform other smaller models at the time of the launch (OpenAI, 2024b).

Gemini-1.5 Pro and Gemini-1.5 Flash

Gemini 1.5 Pro has been introduced by Google in February 2024 (Pichai & Hassabis, 2024), followed by a lighter version with less parameters and quicker response time – Gemini 1.5 Flash in July 2024 (Subramanya, 2024). The two models are found in the top of Lmsys leaderboard (*Chatbot Arena Leaderboard - a Hugging Face Space by Lmsys*, n.d.), together with the OpenAI models. The goal of adding these models to the analysis is exploring alternatives to the GPT models that could potentially have similar or better results.

Mistral-7B-Instruct

Mistral-7B-Instruct (Jiang et al., 2023) is an open-weight model with 7 billion parameters, designed for efficiency without compromising performance. Its open-weight nature allows for local deployment and fine-tuning, enabling customization for specific tasks. Including this

⁴ <https://huggingface.co/google-bert/bert-base-multilingual-cased>

⁵ <https://github.com/google-research/bert>

model in our study helps assess the effectiveness of smaller models in classification tasks, challenging the notion that larger models are always necessary.

DeepSeek-V3

DeepSeek-V3 (DeepSeek-AI, Liu, et al., 2025) is an open-weight model released in January 2025 that has matched or exceeded the performance of leading closed models like GPT-4o and Claude-3.5-Sonnet. It employs a Mixture-of-Experts (MoE) architecture, comprising 671 billion parameters, with 37 billion activated per token. This design enhances efficiency by utilizing only a subset of parameters for each task.

The inclusion of this model in our study aims to assess whether an open-weight model can achieve results comparable to large closed models for the given classification task. However, due to limited API access and insufficient computational resources for self-deployment, this research will apply DeepSeek-V3 only to the manually classified small dataset.

Results

Embedding results

For our embedding experiments that serve primarily to reduce the number of disciplines and secondarily to select custom examples, we have compared several models: e5_mistral_7B, bge-m3, multilingual-e5-large, bert_multilingual, ada_002, text-embedding-3-small, and text-embedding-3-large. We have compared the 3 metrics described in section Number of disciplines and discipline information: N , $Prop_{journals}$, $Prop_{true_labels}$. The OpenAI models (ada_002, text-embedding-3-small, text-embedding-3-large) outperform the other models on this task and have similar results for all the experiments. Therefore, we have decided to continue with text-embedding-3-small. Table 2 presents the results with text-embedding-3-small with the journal being represented by the embeddings of the journal title + examples as it has significantly outperformed the embeddings of only the journal title. Surprisingly, when comparing with the embedding of the train journals, embedding only the title of the training journals yields better results in term of N than when adding the examples.

Table 2: The results for evaluating strategies to reduce the number of labels

<i>Discipline embedding</i>	<i>Other unit</i>	N	$Prop_{journals}$	$Prop_{true_labels}$
Discipline + Description	-	5	0.56	0.65
	-	10	0.70	0.79
	-	20	0.89	0.94
Discipline + Keyword list	-	5	0.20	0.33
	-	10	0.33	0.48
	-	20	0.53	0.65
Average embedding	keywords	5	0.83	0.88
		10	0.87	0.92
		20	0.93	0.96
Individual embeddings	keywords	20 kw	0.84	0.90
		40 kw	10.97	0.91

	60 kw	14.70	0.92	0.95
	80 kw	17.65	0.94	0.96
Individual train journals only title embeddings	20 journ.	7.69	0.86	0.91
	40 journ.	11.07	0.91	0.95
	60 journ.	13.39	0.94	0.97
	80 journ.	15.44	0.96	0.98

The results suggest that using individual keywords and journals instead of having one embedding per discipline yields overall better results as we manage to achieve similar or even better $Prop_{journals}$ and $Prop_{true_labels}$ with a lower N .

The results in Table 2 correspond to the results for the manually classified dataset, however they are not statistically different from the ones for the full dataset and the $Prop_{true_labels}$ is similar to the results for the Norwegian data.

VABB manual classification dataset results

In this subsection we evaluate how well the models perform on the dataset containing manual classifications. We present only the results for a reduced number of disciplines obtained from the 40 closest keywords and 40 closest journals as this configuration performs the best in most cases. Thus, we retain this configuration for further analysis.

Table 3: Results for the classification of the manual dataset. Bold formatting indicates experiments achieving top-three values in both Micro-F1 and Macro-F1 scores.

Experiment	Model	Simple prompt		Complex prompt	
		Micro-F1	Macro-F1	Micro-F1	Macro-F1
All disciplines and fixed examples	gpt-4o-2024-08-06	0.66	0.47	0.60	0.42
	gpt-4o-mini-2024-07-18	0.57	0.50	0.56	0.49
	gemini-1.5-pro-001	0.61	0.45	0.57	0.43
	gemini-1.5-flash-001	0.57	0.47	0.55	0.44
	mistralai/Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.1	0.46	0.33	0.40	0.29
	deepseek-ai/DeepSeek-V3	0.62	0.45	0.58	0.42
All disciplines and custom examples	gpt-4o-2024-08-06	0.68	0.51	0.65	0.48
	gpt-4o-mini-2024-07-18	0.65	0.48	0.64	0.49
	gemini-1.5-pro-001	0.67	0.49	0.58	0.43
	gemini-1.5-flash-001	0.61	0.49	0.57	0.46
	mistralai/Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.1	0.51	0.39	0.44	0.33
	deepseek-ai/DeepSeek-V3	0.65	0.53	0.60	0.49
Disciplines reduced by individual keywords embeddings proximity (40), fixed examples	gpt-4o-2024-08-06	0.65	0.47	0.63	0.44
	gpt-4o-mini-2024-07-18	0.63	0.47	0.63	0.45
	gemini-1.5-pro-001	0.67	0.47	0.61	0.44
	gemini-1.5-flash-001	0.65	0.45	0.60	0.43
	mistralai/Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.1	0.53	0.38	0.47	0.33
	deepseek-ai/DeepSeek-V3	0.66	0.46	0.61	0.44
Disciplines reduced by individual keywords embeddings proximity (40), custom examples	gpt-4o-2024-08-06	0.69	0.50	0.66	0.48
	gpt-4o-mini-2024-07-18	0.67	0.51	0.68	0.49
	gemini-1.5-pro-001	0.69	0.48	0.61	0.44
	gemini-1.5-flash-001	0.66	0.48	0.59	0.44
	mistralai/Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.1	0.57	0.39	0.50	0.38
	deepseek-ai/DeepSeek-V3	0.68	0.50	0.61	0.46
	gpt-4o-2024-08-06	0.63	0.47	0.61	0.45

Disciplines reduced by train journals embeddings proximity (40), fixed examples	gpt-4o-mini-2024-07-18	0.59	0.47	0.58	0.42
	gemini-1.5-pro-001	0.65	0.47	0.60	0.44
	gemini-1.5-flash-001	0.60	0.48	0.59	0.48
	mistralai/Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.1	0.54	0.45	0.46	0.34
	deepseek-ai/DeepSeek-V3	0.63	0.45	0.59	0.42
Disciplines reduced by train journals embeddings proximity (40), custom examples	gpt-4o-2024-08-06	0.69	0.52	0.66	0.51
	gpt-4o-mini-2024-07-18	0.66	0.50	0.67	0.49
	gemini-1.5-pro-001	0.68	0.51	0.58	0.44
	gemini-1.5-flash-001	0.64	0.52	0.58	0.49
	mistralai/Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.1	0.56	0.44	0.49	0.37
	deepseek-ai/DeepSeek-V3	0.67	0.53	0.61	0.49
BERT multilingual		0.59	0.58		

The results from Table 3 show that GPT-4o models, Gemini models and DeepSeek-V3 perform similarly in terms of micro-F1 score, while Mistral-7B-Instruct lags behind. mBERT has the highest macro-F1 score and provides the most balanced results across disciplines. However, the large language models perform better on the disciplines that are the most represented in the dataset. The results illustrate clearly that the reduction of the number of disciplines has a big impact on the smaller models, while providing custom examples improves the results in all the experiments. For the next parts, to simplify the analysis and reduce the costs, we provide only the results with custom examples on the small models. Additional results are published on Github⁶.

An interesting finding is that asking the model to generate additional information about a journal and then using it as context seems to have a negative impact on the results. One possible explanation is that the models frequently hallucinate, introducing noise into the prompt. To investigate this, we manually extracted journal and conference descriptions from official sources when available. For 12 instances, no clear description could be found.

Table 4: Comparison of embeddings between model-generated and manually extracted descriptions. An asterisk (*) indicates cases where the model provided descriptions for multiple instances without a corresponding manually retrieved description.

⁶ https://github.com/Cristinutaa/journal_classification

Model	# with summary	mean cosine similarity	min cosine similarity	max cosine similarity
gpt-4o-2024-08-06	58	0.84	0.63	0.93
gpt-4o-mini-2024-07-18	45	0.81	0.57	0.95
gemini-1.5-pro-001	188*	0.79	0.17	0.94
gemini-1.5-flash-001	179*	0.79	0.31	0.95
mistralai/Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.1	216*	0.76	0.30	0.96
deepseek-ai/DeepSeek-V3	126*	0.81	0.53	0.93

Table 4 provides the mean, minimum, and maximum cosine similarity values between manually extracted descriptions and those generated by the models, using text-embedding-3-small for embedding computation. The results suggest that GPT models and DeepSeek generate summaries that closely align with manually retrieved descriptions, but for fewer examples, whereas Gemini and Mistral produce more errors while maintaining high similarity for most instances.

These findings contradict our hypothesis that the performance drop is primarily due to hallucinations. While high vector similarity suggests a degree of semantic overlap, it does not necessarily mean that the generated text accurately represents the same entity or concept.

Agreement with human reviewers

The results from the previous experiment should be interpreted in the context of human classification variability. The final classification assigned to journals and conference proceedings in the dataset is the result of a multi-reviewer process designed to reduce subjectivity. Specifically, five reviewers (R0–R4) contribute to the classification, with two reviewers assessing each journal or conference proceeding independently. If their classifications fully align, this becomes the final classification. In cases of disagreement, a designated reviewer (R0) makes the final decision.

This subsection uses two main metrics: full agreement when all the disciplines proposed by the two reviewers match exactly and partial agreement when at least one proposed discipline is the same. By definition, full agreement is a subset of partial agreement and is therefore included in its measurement.

Table 5 presents the agreement rates among reviewer pairs. Full agreement is often below 0.5, while the partial agreement is mostly over 0.6. These results highlight the complexity of the classification task as reviewers frequently partially or fully disagree with each other.

Table 5: Reviewers agreement rates with each other

Reviewers pair	Full agreement	Partial agreement
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R1 – R0	0.53	0.80
R2 – R1	0.31	0.57
R3 – R2	0.27	0.61
R4 – R3	0.45	0.80
R0 – R4	0.47	0.67

Table 6 shows the results for each reviewer when compared to the experiment in which the number of candidate disciplines was reduced by retaining only those assigned to the 40 closest journals in the embedding space. Additionally, it reports how well each reviewer’s classification aligns with the final classification.

Gemini-1.5-Pro achieves the highest proportion of classifications fully matching those assigned by most reviewers, while DeepSeek-V3 aligns most frequently with at least one assigned discipline per journal or conference proceeding.

Table 6: Reviewers' agreement rates with LLM results using a reduced discipline list based on the 40 closest journals and custom examples, and the final classification. Bold formatting indicates the best full and partial matches for each reviewer.

		R0	R1	R2	R3	R4	Top 1
Nb. items	-	102	98	98	98	98	
gpt-4o-2024-08-06	Full	0.29	0.36	0.22	0.33	0.27	1
	Partial	0.79	0.82	0.66	0.85	0.82	2
gemini-1.5-pro-001	Full	0.38	0.41	0.32	0.33	0.39	5
	Partial	0.73	0.71	0.62	0.81	0.81	1
deepseek-ai/DeepSeek-V3	Full	0.33	0.33	0.17	0.31	0.27	0
	Partial	0.80	0.79	0.66	0.90	0.85	4
mistralai/Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.1	Full	0.26	0.32	0.19	0.30	0.29	0
	Partial	0.66	0.69	0.57	0.70	0.70	0
final classification	Full	0.62	0.57	0.47	0.55	0.59	
	Partial	0.86	0.81	0.61	0.92	0.81	

To better understand if in case of disagreement or partial disagreement the classification is unreasonable, we present three examples of classification disagreement:

Example 1: journal “Comunità internazionale” (ISSN: 0010-5066)

- **R0:** Social and economic geography
- **R1:** Law
- **Final classification:** Law, Social and economic geography
- **GPT-4o:** Political science, Sociology
- **Gemini-1.5-Pro :** Political science
- **Deepseek-V3 :** Political science
- **Mistral-7B-Instruct :** Sociology, Economics and business

Example 2: journal “Architectural research in Finland” (ISSN: 2489-6799)

- **R3:** Social and economic geography, Arts (arts, history of arts, performing arts, music)
- **R4:** Civil engineering
- **Final classification:** Arts (arts, history of arts, performing arts, music)
- **GPT-4o:** Civil engineering, Social and economic geography, Arts (arts, history of arts, performing arts, music)
- **Gemini-1.5-Pro :** Civil engineering, Arts (arts, history of arts, performing arts, music)
- **Deepseek-V3 :** Civil engineering, Arts (arts, history of arts, performing arts, music)
- **Mistral-7B-Instruct :** Civil engineering

Example 3: journal “INSAM” (ISSN: 2637-1898)

Note: the full name (not provided to the models) is INSAM Journal of Contemporary Music, Art and Technology

- **R3:** Arts (arts, history of arts, performing arts, music)
- **R4:** Arts (arts, history of arts, performing arts, music)
- **Final classification:** Arts (arts, history of arts, performing arts, music)
- **GPT-4o:** Arts (arts, history of arts, performing arts, music), Media and communications
- **Gemini-1.5-Pro :** Computer and information sciences
- **Deepseek-V3 :** Arts (arts, history of arts, performing arts, music), Psychology
- **Mistral-7B-Instruct :** Computer and information sciences, Media and communications, Educational sciences

In the first example, although the journal’s name could suggest a focus on political science, its description states that its primary focus is international law, community law, administrative law, constitutional law, Roman law, labor law, and philosophy of law. The models did not generate a summary for this journal, indicating that the classification was likely based solely on the journal name. The same applies to the second example.

In the third example, the classification deviates even further from reality, as the models only had the journal's name to rely on, and the provided name is an abbreviation, making it even more difficult to infer the correct classification.

VABB full data results

Table 7 presents the results for a subsample of the full VABB dataset, which includes journals and conference proceedings in various languages and with varying levels of classification difficulty. Table 8 separates the results by difficulty level, focusing on the experiment with a reduced number of disciplines, where only disciplines represented in the 40 closest journals (based on cosine similarity of embeddings) were retained, along with custom examples.

Our hypothesis that journals indexed in more international databases are classified more accurately is confirmed. Additionally, when considering only manually classified publications

and using their manual classification as ground truth, classification results improve. This suggests that model predictions align more closely with human classifications than with classifications from a single database.

However, contrary to the initial intuition that a more diverse dataset with easier-to-classify publications would improve performance, models achieve a lower micro-F1 score on this dataset compared to the subset with manually classified journals. At the same time, macro-F1 scores improve, suggesting that greater sample diversity leads to more balanced classification performance across disciplines.

This discrepancy is largely due to differences in discipline distribution across datasets. The manually classified subset from recent iterations contains many samples in disciplines such as Arts, History, Computer and Information Sciences, Law, Literature, Philosophy and Ethics, Educational Sciences, Languages and Linguistics, and Religion, which models classify with relative ease. Meanwhile, the larger dataset was selected to improve disciplinary and linguistic balance, resulting in a higher proportion of journals and conference proceedings from disciplines and languages that models struggle to classify.

Table 7: Results for the extended VABB-SHW journal list

<i>Experiment</i>	<i>Model</i>	Simple prompt		Complex prompt	
		<i>Micro-F1</i>	<i>Macro-F1</i>	<i>Micro-F1</i>	<i>Macro-F1</i>
All disciplines and custom examples	gpt-4o-mini-2024-07-18	0.52	0.51	0.52	0.50
	gemini-1.5-flash-001	0.51	0.50	0.46	0.7
	mistralai/Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.1	0.42	0.39	0.36	0.34
Disciplines reduced by individual keywords embeddings proximity (40), custom examples	gpt-4o-mini-2024-07-18	0.53	0.49	0.53	0.49
	gemini-1.5-flash-001	0.52	0.48	0.48	0.44
	mistralai/Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.1	0.43	0.39	0.41	0.37
Disciplines reduced by train journals embeddings proximity (40), custom examples	gpt-4o-mini-2024-07-18	0.53	0.51	0.53	0.51
	gemini-1.5-flash-001	0.53	0.49	0.48	0.44
	mistralai/Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.1	0.43	0.40	0.39	0.37
BERT multilingual		0.49	0.33		

Table 8: Analysis of classification results by difficulty level and when considering only the manual classification as the ground truth. Results are based on the 40 closest journals in embedding cosine similarity to the one classified and custom examples.

	Easy		Medium		High		Only manual	
	Micro-F1	Macro-F1	Micro-F1	Macro-F1	Micro-F1	Macro-F1	Micro-F1	Macro-F1
gpt-4o-mini-2024-07-18	0.63	0.58	0.51	0.49	0.46	0.41	0.50	0.43
gemini-1.5-flash-001	0.62	0.56	0.50	0.46	0.45	0.39	0.50	0.42
mistralai/Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.1	0.51	0.47	0.41	0.39	0.36	0.30	0.38	0.31

Norwegian data results

The results for the Norwegian dataset surpass those for the large VABB dataset, which is expected given that classification is limited to a single discipline. Similar to the large VABB dataset, the Norwegian dataset was selected to maintain a balance across languages and disciplines, which explains its lower micro-F1 score compared to the manually classified VABB dataset.

Table 9: Results for the Norwegian data

<i>Experiment</i>	<i>Model</i>	Simple prompt		Complex prompt	
		<i>Micro-F1</i>	<i>Macro-F1</i>	<i>Micro-F1</i>	<i>Macro-F1</i>
All disciplines and custom examples	gpt-4o-mini-2024-07-18	0.61	0.59	0.57	0.56
	gemini-1.5-flash-001	0.62	0.60	0.60	0.58
	mistralai/Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.1	0.50	0.48	0.49	0.46
Disciplines reduced by individual keywords embeddings proximity (40), custom examples	gpt-4o-mini-2024-07-18	0.60	0.57	0.56	0.53
	gemini-1.5-flash-001	0.61	0.58	0.59	0.56
	mistralai/Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.1	0.51	0.48	0.47	0.44
Disciplines reduced by train journals embeddings proximity (40), custom examples	gpt-4o-mini-2024-07-18	0.60	0.59	0.59	0.58
	gemini-1.5-flash-001	0.63	0.62	0.60	0.59
	mistralai/Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.1	0.51	0.50	0.45	0.43
	BERT multilingual	0.59	0.57		

Conclusions and Future Work

This study has explored the use of large language models (LLMs) to assist in the classification of journals and conference proceedings into predefined disciplines, specifically the taxonomy proposed by OECD FORD. We tested five model families – both open-weight and closed corporate models. GPT, Gemini, and DeepSeek models demonstrated comparable performance across experiments. Mistral underperformed, which is expected given its smaller size. While fine-tuned mBERT was generally outperformed by the generative models, it achieved a higher macro-F1 score on the VABB manual dataset.

We investigated multiple dimensions of the classification problem.

The first dimension concerned the datasets. The VABB manual dataset contains journals and conference proceedings newly added in the latest cycle of data collection, which were not found in any of the consulted international databases. For this dataset, we used the final classification – decided after two annotators' input – as ground truth. Results were promising, with certain configurations achieving a micro-F1 score above 0.65 and macro-F1 above 0.5. The second dataset consisted of a more balanced subset of VABB-SHW, including journals indexed in international databases. We grouped them into three difficulty levels based on the number of external sources in which each journal could be found. While macro-F1 scores remained similar to the manual dataset, micro-F1 scores were lower due to balanced representation across disciplines—some of which are harder to classify. Two conclusions emerge: journals better represented in external sources are more accurately classified, and LLMs agree more with manual classifications than with those extracted from international databases.

The second dimension explored was prompt structure and content. A chained prompting strategy – where the model first generates a summary of the journal and then uses it for classification – did not improve results. However, initial analyses based on embedding similarity suggest the issue is not necessarily with the summaries themselves. Since embedding similarity does not capture fine-grained factual accuracy or alignment with the journal's scope, a more thorough manual review is needed to evaluate the quality of the generated summaries.

We also showed that including custom examples – selected based on embedding similarity to the journal being classified – yields significantly better results than random examples. Furthermore, reducing the number of candidate disciplines by retaining only those associated with the closest keywords or already-classified journals—where proximity is determined via embedding similarity—had a small but consistent positive effect, despite the potential for compound error introduced by the possibility of the lack of inclusion of all true labels in the reduced list.

The third dimension explored was the impact of the number of labels to be predicted, addressed by introducing the Norwegian journal list. As expected, models performed better on this single-label dataset compared to the multi-label VABB-SHW.

Lastly, we analyzed how model predictions compare to manual classifications and inter-annotator agreement. Human annotators showed high disagreement, with full agreement peaking at 0.53 and partial agreement at 0.8. Gemini-1.5-Pro achieved the highest full agreement with all annotators, while DeepSeek-V3 showed the highest partial agreement with four out of five annotators. Although model-human full agreement does not surpass inter-human agreement, partial agreement reaches 0.9 in some cases. A qualitative error analysis revealed that models struggle when the journal name is counter-intuitive or abbreviated in the context where no additional information is available. As the models used in our study lacked internet access, abbreviation handling remains a challenge. This could be mitigated by expanding abbreviations and ensuring full titles are provided in the data.

Returning to our core question—can these models assist in journal classification?—the answer is cautiously optimistic. Generative models are often able to identify accurate information, but human oversight remains necessary. These tools show strong potential as assistants, but not as replacements.

Limitations and Future Work

Several potential improvements were not addressed in this paper – either because they were beyond its intended scope or became apparent during the course of the research.

First, with the exception of mBERT, we used the models without fine-tuning. As discussed in the literature, fine-tuning smaller models could offer a viable and cost-effective alternative to large closed models, especially if they are further exposed to journal-related data.

Second, we did not assess model confidence in its predictions. Future work could be built on approaches like Mayer et al. (2023), where confident model responses are accepted automatically, and human reviewers interfere only when the model is uncertain. However, additional study is required to determine if confidence correlates with accuracy.

Third, unlike human annotators who could consult online resources, models had no internet access. In practice, this meant they relied solely on basic metadata such as title and ISSN, or on generated summaries that may be prone to hallucination. Better results might be achieved by integrating verified information about the journal scope or enabling web access.

Fourth, due to the rapid development cycle of LLMs – e.g., GPT models are updated every few months – the models evaluated here may already be outdated. Our findings should therefore be seen as a snapshot of model capabilities at the time of the experiments, not a permanent benchmark. If the results seem promising, we encourage replication using newer models, which could yield better performance.

A fundamental limitation that cannot be solved with better models alone is the subjectivity of the classification task, as shown in our comparative analysis with human annotators. Our study joins others (Goh et al., 2020) that have used reviewers for the task of publication-level or journal-level classification in their conclusion that the task of classifying research output is inherently difficult and the level of disagreement is significant.

Finally, closed models present reproducibility challenges, since companies can restrict access at any time (Y. (YJ) Chae & Davidson, 2023). Our inclusion of high-performing open-weight alternatives like DeepSeek-V3 helps address this concern by providing options that are less subject to such constraints.

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